

D.1.2.2 Report - Pilot PT on typing/characterization including WGS

Workpackage 1

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List of abbreviations

AMI: Amikacin
AMP: Ampicillin
AMR: Antimicrobial resistance
AZI: Azithromycin
CHL: Chloramphenicol
CIP: Ciprofloxacin
COL: Colistin
ERY: Erythromycin
ETP: Ertapenem
EURL: European Union Reference Laboratory
FEP: Cefepime
FOT: Cefotaxime
FOX: Cefoxitin
GEN: Gentamicin
IMI: Imipenem
IQR: Inter quantile range
KAN: Kanamycin
MERO: Meropenem
MLST: Multi-locus sequence typing
PT: proficiency test
SDSTR: Standard deviation
SMX: Sulfamethoxazole
STR: Streptomycin
TAZ: Ceftazidime
TET: Tetracycline
TMP: Trimethoprim
WGS: Whole genome sequencing

WP1-T2-ST2: DTU GENOMIC PROFICIENCY TEST 2021 – DATA SUMMARY

1. Introduction

In 2010, all European Union Reference Laboratories (EURLs) were evaluated. In the overall report, an encouragement was stated to seek better use of the material utilized for the proficiency tests (PT) offered annually to the national reference laboratories in Europe. The intention was to make better use of the funding provided to the EURLs, to strengthen collaboration across the EURLs, to provide added value and cost savings. Thus, the overall intention with the WP1-T2-ST2 PT, provided in EJP CARE, was to collaborate with the other EURLs towards identifying suitable reference material, which could be potentially available to be used, by EURLs and other laboratories, in the future for method validation and PTs, and by that save costs and labor.

The main objective of the Genomic PT2021 was to quantify differences among laboratories, to facilitate the development of reliable laboratory results of consistently good quality within the area of DNA preparation, sequencing, and analysis, e.g., detection of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) genes, multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) and serotyping. This ensures that the discrepancies and differences among laboratories are known and will contribute to the standardization of whole genome sequencing (WGS) and data analysis, with the aim to produce comparable data for monitoring and research purposes. The present report summarises the findings of the Genomic PT conducted in 2021 for the EJP CARE consortium. The participating laboratories are listed, in alphabetical order, in Table 1 and were arbitrarily assigned codes (EJP01 to EJP15) which are used throughout the present report. Moreover, the scoring system and overviews of the obtained scores are presented in detail. Please note that the participants' evaluation was not expressed on a pass/fail basis, and the participants are therefore encouraged to self-evaluate their performance, applying internal acceptance criteria.

Table 1. EJP CARE laboratories (n=15) participating in the Genomic PT2021, presented in alphabetical order.

Name of institute/organization	Country
Animal and Plant Health Agency (APHA)	United Kingdom
Finnish Food Authority	Finland
Institute of Food Safety, Animal Health and Environment "BIOR"	Latvia
Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Department of Food Safety, Nutrition and Veterinary Public Health	Italy
Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise "G. Caporale"	Italy
IZSLER, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale Lombardia ed Emilia Romagna	Italy
National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)	Netherlands
National Veterinary Institute, SVA	Sweden
National Veterinary Research Institute	Poland
Public Health Agency of Sweden	Sweden
Public Health England	United Kingdom
Statens Serum Institut	Denmark
Swedish Food Agency	Sweden
Technical University of Denmark – National Food Institute	Denmark
Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR)	Netherlands

The participants of Genomic PT 2021 were requested to perform WGS and bioinformatics analyses on two strains of each of the following species: *Salmonella enterica* (n=2), *Escherichia coli* (n=2) and *Campylobacter coli*/*C. jejuni* (n=2). Strains were selected among partners and EURLs to facilitate the concept of providing reference material for the next PTs. The two *Campylobacter* strains employed in the genomic PT 2021 belonged to the species *C. jejuni* and will be referred to as *C. jejuni* for the rest of the present report. The codes used for

each strain in the Genomic PT2021 are presented in Table 2. For each strain, two types of DNA samples were analysed: 1) DNA isolated from live cultures, referred to as “BACT” and 2) pre-prepared DNA, shipped to the participants, referred to as “DNA”, resulting in twelve (n=12) samples in total. The downstream processing of the samples is presented in Figure 1. The participants were asked to subcultivate the live cultures, which were shipped as swabs, perform DNA extraction and WGS, according to each laboratory’s own pipeline. The pre-prepared DNA was ready to be used downstream for WGS, according to each laboratory’s standard procedure. As paired-end sequence technology is most commonly used, paired-end sequences were requested for this PT; however, two laboratories indicated to use single-end sequences for their standard procedure and were therefore also included.

The participants were requested to report data on the prediction of AMR determinants towards a limited number of antimicrobials for each species (see Table 3), including chromosomal mutations and genes or gene variants. Based on these findings, the participants had to submit the predicted AMR phenotypic profile for each strain. The platform used for data submission (webtool) assigned scores to each submitted result, i.e., chromosomal mutation, gene or gene variant and predicted AMR phenotypic profile. A positive score (score=1) was assigned for each submitted result that was expected, while a zero score (score=0) was assigned for cases where expected results were not reported, or when deviating results were reported. The individual evaluation report for each participant can be downloaded from the webtool.

Table 2. Strains included in the Genomic PT2021. Two types of samples were analysed for each strain: DNA isolated from live cultures (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA).

Species	Strain code	Material
S. enterica	GENOMIC21-001	BACT/DNA
	GENOMIC21-002	BACT/DNA
E. coli	GENOMIC21-003	BACT/DNA
	GENOMIC21-004	BACT/DNA
C. jejuni	GENOMIC21-005	BACT/DNA
	GENOMIC21-006	BACT/DNA

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the downstream processing of live culture samples (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA samples (DNA).

The live cultures were sequenced by the EURL-AR at several steps in the sample preparation procedure, to ensure that isolates remained pure. Closed genomes were produced from hybrid assemblies of short-reads, provided by the EURL-AR, and long-reads, provided by collaborating colleagues at the Wageningen Bioveterinary Research (WBVR). Long-reads were generated using Oxford Nanopore Technologies Minlon sequencing using the ligation sequencing kit SQK-LSK109 with Native Barcoding and flowcell R9.4.1. Short-reads and long-reads were combined in a hybrid assembly using Unicycler v0.4.8. Contigs that were not yet fully closed were curated manually using assemblies based only on long-read data. Generation of expected results for MLST, AMR determinants and serotype were determined for the closed genomes as well as the multiple rounds of short sequencing reads produced during the sample preparation. AMR genes and chromosomal mutations were identified using ResFinder v4.1, using the default parameters, i.e., 90% identity and 60% coverage. The obtained results were subsequently manually curated. Sequence types were found with the cge tool MLST v2.0, *E. coli* serotypes were determined with SeroTypefinder v2.0, while for *S. enterica* they were obtained with SeqSero 1.2. Species were verified using kmerfinder v3.2.

Table 3. Overview of antimicrobials included in the Genomic PT 2021, for *S. enterica*, *E. coli* and *C. jejuni*.

Antimicrobial	Class	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>
Amikacin	Aminoglycoside	X	X	
Ampicillin	β -lactam	X	X	
Azithromycin	Macrolide	X	X	
Cefepime	β -lactam	X	X	
Cefotaxime	β -lactam	X	X	
Cefoxitin	β -lactam	X	X	
Ceftazidime	β -lactam	X	X	
Chloramphenicol	Amphenicol	X	X	X
Ciprofloxacin	Quinolone	X	X	X
Colistin	Polymyxin	X	X	
Ertapenem	β -lactam	X	X	X
Erythromycin	Macrolide	X	X	X
Gentamicin	Aminoglycoside	X	X	X
Imipenem	β -lactam	X	X	
Kanamycin	Aminoglycoside	X	X	
Meropenem	β -lactam	X	X	
Nalidixic acid	Quinolone	X	X	
Rifampicin	Rifamycin	X	X	
Streptomycin	Aminoglycoside	X	X	
Sulfamethoxazole	Folate pathway antagonist	X	X	
Tetracycline	Tetracycline	X	X	X
Tigecycline	Tetracycline	X	X	
Trimethoprim	Folate pathway antagonist	X	X	

2. Participation in Genomic PT2021

The level of participation of the EJP CARE laboratories in the analysis of the different materials (n=12, see Table 2) included in Genomic PT 2021 is presented in Table 4 and Figure 2. Two laboratories (EJP01 and EJP10) signed up for the analysis of the *E. coli* samples alone (BACT and DNA), therefore participated in 33% of the materials. The rest of the participants analysed all materials provided in the PT (n=12), apart from EJP06 which did not analyse GENOMIC21-001-DNA. In total, all *S. enterica* and *C. jejuni* samples were analysed by 87% of the participants, apart from GENOMIC21-001-DNA which was analysed by 80%. *E. coli* samples were analysed by all participants.

Table 4. Overview of participation in the different materials included in Genomic PT 2021. Grey=not participated.

	<i>S. enterica</i>				<i>E. coli</i>				<i>C. jejuni</i>			
	GENOMIC21-001		GENOMIC21-002		GENOMIC21-003		GENOMIC21-004		GENOMIC21-005		GENOMIC21-006	
	BACT	DNA	BACT	DNA	BACT	DNA	BACT	DNA	BACT	DNA	BACT	DNA
EJP01					x	x	x	x				
EJP02	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP03	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP04	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP05	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP06	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP07	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP08	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP09	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP10					x	x	x	x				
EJP11	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP12	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP13	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP14	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
EJP15	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Figure 2. Percent of materials (ntotal=12) analysed by each laboratory in Genomic PT 2021 (Left) and percent of participants that analysed each sample (Right).

3. Methods

3.1. Quality of sequencing

Submitted raw sequence files were run through internal QC pipeline, utilizing fastqc, quast, spades, bduk2 and bmap (Kristensen *et al.*, 2022¹). The sequence quality was evaluated based on several metrics: average coverage, average insert size, detected MLST, Q-1 score, Q-2 score and size of assembled genome. These parameters were expected to pass corresponding cutoffs, as listed in Table 5. The total number of samples varied in Q-2 score and average insert size, due to two participants submitting single-end reads, for which these two metrics were not relevant. Furthermore, we investigated several metrics which were not used for scoring but provided information on the overall quality of the sequencing. These were N50, percentage of coverage of reference chromosome, percentage of reads mapped to reference genomes and number of contigs >200 bp. These had been identified previously as indicative of overall sequence quality (Kristensen *et al.*, 2022¹) and were evaluated using inter quantile range (IQR) and standard deviation (SD) to determine possible areas for improvement. Underperformance was defined as below 3SD of the mean or 1.5 times IQR below the 1st quantile

¹ Kristensen *et al.*, 2022, "Genomic proficiency testing of laboratories' ability to provide high quality bacterial whole genome sequencing in 2020", *Manuscript in preparation*.

for percentage coverage of the reference chromosome, percentage reads mapped to the reference genome, average insert size, N50 or NG50 and Q-1/Q-2 scores. 3SD above the mean or 1.5 times IQR above the 3rd quantile for number of contigs > 200bp. Both upper and lower thresholds were used for percentage size compared to the reference. A SNP-matrix was constructed using CSI-phylogeny v1.4 to further control clonality of submitted strains, which were expected to have no more than 10 SNPs to the reference. Strains that deviated more than 5% in genome size compared to the reference were evaluated for contamination, with possible exclusion from analysis.

3.2. Analysis of AMR determinants and predicted resistance phenotype

The submitted data about AMR determinants were extracted from the webtool as an Excel file and were manually quality controlled for the accuracy of the scores assigned by the webtool. Each chromosomal mutation, gene or gene variant and predicted AMR phenotypic profile submitted, received a positive score (score=1), if it was expected. On the contrary, expected results that were not reported, as well as reporting of deviating results, obtained a zero score (score=0). The predicted AMR phenotype results were evaluated based on an “all-or-none” approach, i.e., were positively scored (score=1) when the exact and complete expected phenotypic AMR profile was reported; otherwise, submitted profiles obtained a zero score (score=0). In the present report, to evaluate the performance of the participants in more detail, individual scores were assigned to each individual AMR phenotype submitted, instead of scoring the entire phenotypic AMR profile submitted. The performance of the participants regarding the identification of AMR determinants was expressed as percent of the maximum possible score that could be obtained for each strain – see Table 24.

3.3. Analysis of MLST and Serogroup/serotype results

The same scoring principle as above (score=1 for matching expected results, score=0 for missing data or reporting of deviating result) was applied to the MLST data. For the Serogroup/serotype data, the participants were not scored with zero for not reporting expected results or reporting of deviating results, since the submission of data for this field was optional.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Quality of DNA and sequencing

Most participants used an automatic DNA extraction method (60, 67 and 53% for *S. enterica*, *E. coli* and *C. jejuni* respectively), while the rest did manual extraction. Moreover, the majority of participants used Illumina DNA prep or Nextera XT DNA library preparation kits, and MiSeq or NextSeq as sequencing platforms, for all strains. Participants used paired end sequence reads, apart from EJP08 and EJP10, who used single end. The read lengths employed by most participants were 150, 250 or 251 base pairs. Participant EJP15 used a different read length for BACT and DNA samples, 250bp and 300bp respectively. One participant performed trimming of the reads before upload, while two participants did not provide information on it. Details regarding the methods mentioned above are presented in Appendix 1.

A count of samples that passed/failed QC metrics can be found in Table 5. The total number of samples varied in Q-2 score and average insert size, due to two participants submitting single-end reads, for which these two metrics are not relevant. A total of 163 sequences of *S. enterica* (n=51), *E. coli* (n=60) and *C. jejuni* (n=52) were analysed. Of the metrics included in the report to participants, the main issue was average insert size, with 23.8% of submitted strains failing to reach an average of 250bp (single end sequences excluded). For one participant, this metric failed only for the purified DNA, possibly due to degradation, presumably as a result of transportation or storage conditions. For the majority of samples, no clear tendency was observed for the submitter. The most likely reason is that workflows were tailored to produce insert sizes close to or below 250bp, which makes small variations result in only a portion of samples passing. A substantial proportion of participants

(26.7%) sequenced with average read lengths of 150bp, which means a ~50bp overlap in read pairs produces failing insert sizes. A possible remedy would be to select for slightly longer fragments during library preparation.

Two samples failed on genome size, one presumably a contamination as the genome was 144% compared to the reference. The other varied by 5.1%, failing the cutoff by 0.1%; it was deemed appropriate to include the sample in further analysis as it passed remaining metrics. A single sample failed the average coverage of >20x. Likely explained by the fact that the specific sequence file from the participant had relatively few reads compared to their other submissions, indicating a low yield compared to the general performance of their workflow. MLST, Q-score R1/R2 received passing scores for all participants

The metrics previously found to indicate overall sequence quality, see Kristensen *et al.*, 2022 (footnote 1, page 8) were likewise evaluated. The results are summarized as boxplots in Appendix 2: Boxplots of the evaluated QC metrics, while the relevant QC metrics are presented in Appendix 3: QC metrics. Percentage coverage of the reference chromosome was evaluated, but thresholds were highly sensitive as most sequence submissions were able to cover the chromosome nearly in its entirety. All accepted samples covered more than 99.7% of the chromosome, making this metric less informative for overall performance. For percentage reads mapped to the reference chromosome, 3SD did not detect any outliers, due to high variation among the limited number of samples. The IQR however showed 2 participants achieving less success, with one participant, EJP06, showing low percentage across all three genera. Particularly live culture samples showed issues, possibly indicating a problem in the library preparation.

Regarding the average insert size, we observed only one possible IQR outlier, suggesting that issues with this parameter was systemic to the workflows used, rather than large deviations stemming from unsuccessful sequencing. The metric percentage in size compared to reference genome, identified 3 participants as outliers. With the exception of one, all were within the accepted 5% deviation. One participant, EJP04, had a comparatively larger assembly for all genera in live culture samples. The cause for this overestimation or redundancy in assembly is unknown, but it could be speculated to arise from residual contamination or sequencing error.

While Q-scores were above accepted threshold for all participants, Q-scores for R1 were markedly lower for EJP08 than other participants, while EJP14 had comparably low Q-scores for R2 in 3 *S. enterica* and 1 *E. coli* samples. The lower performance for EJP08 is most likely due to difference in sequencing platform and preparation kit, but for EJP14 the reason is unknown.

For the number of contigs above 200bp, multiple participants were outliers in IQR, though only one was 3SD from the mean. Less than 250 contigs for strains GENOMIC21-001, GENOMIC21-002, GENOMIC21-003 and GENOMIC21-005 were attainable for most participants. Less than 50 contigs for GENOMIC21-006 was achievable, with just 3 laboratories having no more than 75 contigs. GENOMIC21-004 was remarkably difficult to sequence and the majority of participants had more than 400 contigs >200bp. Markedly, EJP04, EJP06 and EJP13 had multiple samples which showed comparably high number of contigs. EJP04 samples for GENOMIC21-003-BACT and GENOMIC21-005-BACT are likely linked to the issues discussed previously for this participant. EJP06 samples of GENOMIC21-001-BACT, GENOMIC21-002-DNA and both isolates of GENOMIC21-003, may be due to the low proportion of reads mapped to the reference. In this case, the assembly size does not indicate contamination. Possibly high DNA concentration combined with low amount of reagents lead to incomplete coverage of the genome, but it is likewise possible that the fault lies with reagents or in the automated process. For EJP13 the other evaluated metrics did not further indicate issues in the sequencing.

Table 5. Cutoffs used in the Genomic PT2021 and number of samples passing said cutoffs.

Metric	Cut-off	Passed samples				Failed samples			
		Total	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>	Total	<i>S. enterica</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>C. jejuni</i>
Average coverage	>20x	162	50	60	52	1	1	0	0
Average insert size	>250bp	112	36	39	37	35	11	13	11
MLST	Match	163	51	60	52	0	0	0	0
Q-1 score	>20	163	51	60	52	0	0	0	0
Q-2 score	>20	147	47	52	48	0	0	0	0
Size of assembled genome	±5%	161	51	59	51	2	0	1	1

N50 and NG50 were considered together as minimal difference was observed between the two metrics. In general, participants achieved satisfactory N50s, the lowest being 38,949. However, the majority of laboratories could achieve an N50 of more than 100,000 for all samples. EJP06 produced relatively low N50s, already indicated by the poorer mapping results for the participant. The N50/NG50 metric have been found to correlate strongly with percentage of reads mapped to the reference, see Kristensen *et al.*, 2022 (footnote 1, page 8). EJP12 were likewise identified previously as underperforming by IQR, in this case by coverage of the reference chromosome. This laboratory produced relatively low N50 across all genera. Intuitively, a consequence of improper coverage of the reference genome.

SNP matrices were created for each bacterial strain. Only strain GENOMIC21-006 showed less than 10 SNPs for all submitted isolates. Strains GENOMIC21-002 and GENOMIC21-003 had a few samples with slightly more (≤13 SNPs). In GENOMIC21-005 most strains had between 11-19 SNPs. GENOMIC21-001 had 3 samples (EJP11-001-BACT, EJP14-001-BACT and EJP15-001-BACT) with relatively high number of differences. In GENOMIC21-004, 5 samples deviated slightly (EJP05-BACT, EJP10-BACT, EJP13-BACT, EJP15-BACT and EJP15-DNA) - see Appendix 4: SNP matrices. The number of SNP deviations were unexpected, although still indicating a close phylogenetic relationship. The isolates sent to participants were produced in batch, but the references were constructed at a later date from a subsequent culturing. This has likely caused the issue seen in GENOMIC21-005, where most strains deviate more than expected. Presumably, the same can explain the deviations observed in GENOMIC21-002, -003 and -004. Another possibility lies in the analysis, as the pipeline is continually updated, and a complete reference is rarely available. Lastly, storage or shipping time and conditions might contribute. However, further analysis will be conducted to illuminate if an underlying reason for these deviations can be identified.

4.2. Multi-locus sequence typing (MLST) analysis

The expected results for the MLST analysis for each strain are presented in Table 6. All participants reported the expected MLST type and the expected individual allele values. For *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005, laboratories EJP03 (BACT) and EJP12 (BACT and DNA) reported MLST 1071, instead of the expected 1017, even though they identified all the expected individual allele values. Even though this was due a typing mistake, these results were scored with zero. The participants used different bioinformatics tools for the MLST analysis (Figure 4), with PubMLST being the most popular. All tools employed were successful in identifying the expected MLST. Regarding the type of sequences employed for the MLST analysis, most participants used contigs, for all strains (Figure 3 and Table 7).

Table 6. Expected MLST type and allele values for each gene for each strain included in PT 2021.

Gene	Allele values - <i>S. enterica</i>		Gene	Allele values - <i>E. coli</i>		Gene	Allele values - <i>C. jejuni</i>	
	GENOMIC21-001	GENOMIC21-002		GENOMIC21-003	GENOMIC21-004		GENOMIC21-005	GENOMIC21-006
<i>aroC</i>	10	17	<i>adk</i>	9	16	<i>aspA</i>	33	33
<i>dnaN</i>	19	18	<i>tumC</i>	6	4	<i>glnA</i>	39	39
<i>hemD</i>	12	22	<i>gyrB</i>	33	12	<i>gltA</i>	30	30
<i>hisD</i>	9	17	<i>icd</i>	131	16	<i>glyA</i>	82	79
<i>purE</i>	5	5	<i>mdh</i>	24	9	<i>pgm</i>	104	113
<i>sucA</i>	9	21	<i>purA</i>	8	7	<i>tkt</i>	43	47
<i>thrA</i>	2	19	<i>recA</i>	7	7	<i>uncA</i>	41	17
MLST	34	32	MLST	641	21	MLST	1017	860

Table 7. Types of reads (contigs or raw reads) used for MLST analysis by each participant, for *S. enterica*, *E. coli* and *C. jejuni*.

		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>S. enterica</i>	Contigs	/	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	/	-	-	x	x	x
	Raw reads	/	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	/	x	x	-	-	-
<i>E. coli</i>	Contigs	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	-	-	x	x	X
	Raw reads	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	-
<i>C. jejuni</i>	Contigs	/	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	/	-	-	x	x	X
	Raw reads	/	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	/	x	x	-	-	-

Figure 3. Distribution of the types of reads (contigs or raw reads) used for MLST analysis in Genomic PT 2021, for *S. enterica*, *E. coli* and *C. jejuni*.

Figure 4. Distribution of bioinformatics tools used in Genomic PT 2021 for MLST analysis.

4.3. Detection of AMR determinants

For the identification of AMR determinants most participants used contigs, and ResFinder was the main tool employed (Figure 5); however, the following AMR detection tools were also reported: ARIBA, GeneFinder, NCBI AMRfinderPlus, Staramr or other in-house software. Capturing information on the version of the tool or the version of the database used was not part of the analysis.

Figure 5. Distribution of bioinformatics tools used in Genomic PT 2021 to identify AMR determinants.

The expected results for each strain, related to the identification of AMR determinants, as well as the predicted phenotypic AMR profile, are summarized in Table 8. The expected results were re-evaluated after data submission by the participants and the outcome of this re-evaluation was to exclude some results, i.e., blank the relevant scores. An overview of the excluded results, for which the scores are blanked, is presented in Table 9 and in the list below:

1. In the reference genome, gene *tet(M)* in *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001 is present with 96% identity, which was evaluated as too low; therefore, *tet(M)* was excluded from the list of expected genes. Since there is not a universal cutoff value for the lowest accepted percent identity, participants who reported the *tet(M)* gene were not scored with zero.
2. All AMR results for *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-002 were not evaluated. The majority of participants did not identify three AMR genes present on plasmid (*blaCTX-M-1*, *dfrA1* and *dfrA14*) in DNA isolated from cultures (BACT sample). A possible explanation is that the plasmid was lost during culturing and therefore it is not meaningful to evaluate these results. Moreover, we were not able to identify some of the expected resistance genes in the pre-prepared DNA that was sent to the participants; therefore, these results were also excluded.
3. In Appendix 2 of the Genomic PT2021 protocol², on page 7, it is stated that “All genes conferring resistance to the above-mentioned classes of antimicrobials should be reported”. The intention was to report all genes conferring resistance to the antimicrobials mentioned in Table 1 of Appendix 2 of the protocol (footnote 2, page **Error! Bookmark not defined.**), and not the respective classes in general. Some participants submitted resistance genes for the two *C. jejuni* strains GENOMIC21-005 and GENOMIC21-006, which are related to resistance to β -lactams, but not ertapenem, which is the only β -lactam included in this PT for *C. jejuni*. For this reason, it was decided to exclude these results from evaluation; therefore, the respective scores were blanked.
4. Results regarding the chromosomal mutation T86I in *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006 are not evaluated because of issues regarding the reference *gyrA* gene used in the ResFinder database. Predicted phenotype

² PROTOCOL for DTU Genomic Proficiency Test 2021, 2021, EURL-AR.

resistant to ciprofloxacin is not evaluated too, i.e., phenotypes resistant or susceptible to ciprofloxacin were accepted.

- In the reference genome, gene *tet(O)* in *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006 is present with 95% identity, which was evaluated as too low; therefore, scores for reporting the *tet(O)* gene were blanked and predicted phenotypes resistant or susceptible to tetracycline were accepted. Moreover, if reporting the *tet(O/32/O)* gene, scores were blanked due to relatively similar percentages of identity of *tet(O)* and *tet(O/32/O)* observed in the reference assembled genomes.

Table 8. Expected AMR results for each strain. The AMR determinants marked in yellow, and the respective AMR phenotypes are excluded from evaluation (scores are blanked) – see text. Gene *aac(6’)-laa* is a cryptic gene in *Salmonella*; therefore, even though it is present in the sequences of both *Salmonella* strains included in this PT, it is not expected to confer resistance to AMI phenotypically.

Strain code	Resistance Element	Type	Antimicrobial	Antimicrobial Class	Predicted phenotype R/S
GENOMIC21-001	<i>aph(3’)-Ia</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Kanamycin	Aminoglycoside	R
	<i>blaTEM-1A/B/C/D</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Ampicillin	β-lactam	R
	<i>cmIA1</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Chloramphenicol	Amphenicol	R
	<i>dfrA12</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Trimethoprim	Folate pathway antagonist	R
	<i>mcr-1.1</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Colistin	Polymyxin	R
	<i>mef(B)</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Azithromycin Erythromycin	Macrolide	R
	<i>sul3</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Sulfamethoxazole	Folate pathway antagonist	R
	<i>tet(B)</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Tetracycline	Tetracycline	R
	<i>aac(6’)-laa</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Amikacin	Aminoglycoside	S
	<i>aadA1, ant(3’)-Ia</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Streptomycin	Aminoglycoside	R
	<i>aadA2, aadA2b</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Streptomycin	Aminoglycoside	R
	GENOMIC21-003	<i>blaNDM-4</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Ampicillin	β-lactam
Cefepime				R	
Cefotaxime				R	
Cefoxitin				R	
Ceftazidime				R	
Ertapenem				R	
Imipenem				R	
Meropenem		R			
<i>blaTEM-1A/B/C/D</i>		Gene/Gene Var.	Ampicillin	β-lactam	R
<i>dfrA12</i>		Gene/Gene Var.	Trimethoprim	Folate pathway antagonist	R
<i>sul1</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Sulfamethoxazole	Folate pathway antagonist	R	
<i>sul3</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Sulfamethoxazole	Folate pathway antagonist	R	
<i>aadA2, aadA2b</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Streptomycin	Aminoglycoside	R	
GENOMIC21-004	<i>aph(3’)-Ib</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Streptomycin	Aminoglycoside	R
	<i>aph(6’)-Id</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Streptomycin	Aminoglycoside	R
	<i>sul2</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Sulfamethoxazole	Folate pathway antagonist	R
	<i>tet(B)</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Tetracycline	Tetracycline	R
GENOMIC21-005	A2075G	Chr. Mutation	Erythromycin	Macrolide, 23S rRNA	R
	<i>tet(O)</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Tetracycline	Tetracycline	R
GENOMIC21-006	A2075G	Chr. Mutation	Erythromycin	Macrolide, 23S rRNA	R
	T86I	Chr. Mutation	Ciprofloxacin	Quinolone, <i>gyrA</i>	R
	<i>aph(2’)-If</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Gentamicin	Aminoglycoside	R
	<i>cat</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Chloramphenicol	Amphenicol	R
	<i>tet(O)</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Tetracyclin	Tetracycline	R
	<i>aac(6’)-aph(2’)</i>	Gene/Gene Var.	Gentamicin	Aminoglycoside	R

Table 9. Overview of changes in expected AMR results and re-evaluation of the respective scores.

Strain	AMR determinant or AMR phenotype	Change
GENOMIC21-001	Gene <i>tet(M)</i>	Scores are blanked.
GENOMIC21-002	All AMR determinants (chromosomal mutations, gene/gene variant, predicted AMR phenotype)	Scores are blanked.
GENOMIC21-005	Genes <i>blaOXA-61, blaOXA-193, blaOXA-450, blaOXA-451, blaOXA-452, blaOXA-453, blaOXA-489</i>	Scores are blanked.
GENOMIC21-006	Chromosomal mutation T86I	Scores are blanked.
	Genes <i>ant(6)-Ia, aph(3’)-III, blaOXA-61, blaOXA-193, blaOXA-450, blaOXA-451, blaOXA-452, blaOXA-453, blaOXA-489, tet(O)</i>	Scores are blanked.
	Predicted phenotype R to CIP	Phenotypes with or without CIP accepted (score=1)
	Predicted phenotype R to TET	Phenotypes with or without TET accepted (score=1)

S. enterica, GENOMIC21-001

From the 15 EJP CARE laboratories, 13 and 12 signed up for the analysis of GENOMIC21-001-BACT and GENOMIC21-001-DNA, respectively. Overviews of the submitted data for the *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001 are presented in Table 10 and Figure 6, for AMR genes or gene variants, and in Table 11, Figure 7 and Figure 8, for the predicted AMR phenotype.

All participants (n=13 for BACT, n=12 for DNA) submitted data on AMR gene identification; however, four participants did not report any data on the predicted AMR phenotype (EJP04, EJP05, EJP07 and EJP11) for both BACT and DNA samples. These four laboratories are referred to as “blank-phenotype laboratories” in the following paragraphs. The genes *bla*TEM-1A/B/C/D, *dfrA12*, *mcr-1.1* and *sul3* were identified by all participants, in both BACT and DNA samples. The respective predicted phenotypes resistant to AMP, TMP, COL and SMX, were reported by all participants too, except the “blank-phenotype laboratories” – see above. The gene *mef(B)*, which confers resistance to the macrolides AZI and ERY, was identified by all participants. Resistance to AZI was reported by all the laboratories, except for the “blank-phenotype laboratories”, and EJP12, for both DNA and BACT samples. Resistance to ERY was reported by only four laboratories (EJP06, EJP08, EJP12 and EJP13), which corresponds to 31 and 25% of the participants in BACT and DNA respectively (Figure 8).

Regarding genes related to resistance to TET, all participants except for EJP12, reported the *tet(B)* gene. Moreover, eight participants reported the gene *tet(M)*, for both BACT and DNA, which was not in the list of expected genes. This gene was identified in the reference genome too; however, the percent identity value to the reference gene in the ResFinder database (%ID=96) was considered too low to be reliable, and it was therefore excluded from the list of expected genes. Since a universal cutoff value for the lowest reliable percent identity has not been identified yet, scores regarding the *tet(M)* gene in strain GENOMIC21-001 were blanked, i.e., participants did not get a zero score for reporting the *tet(M)* gene. All participants, apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” (see above), predicted a resistant phenotype to TET for BACT samples, however EJP12 reported a sensitive phenotype for TET in the DNA sample only. The gene *aph(3'')-Ia*, which is predicted to confer resistance to KAN, was identified by 62 and 67% of the participants in BACT and DNA samples respectively (Figure 6). Laboratories EJP03 and EJP12 did not report either the gene or the predicted phenotype resistant to KAN. Laboratory EJP06 reported the gene *aph(3'')-Ia* plus a predicted phenotype resistant to KAN. Even though this is most likely a typing mistake, the submission of this gene was scored with zero, due to incorrect reporting.

Regarding the genes *aadA1* (or variant *ant(3'')-Ia*) and *aadA2* (or variant *aadA2b*), each predicted to confer resistance to STR, they were reported by 62-69% of the participants (Figure 6). Three laboratories (EJP03, EJP04 and EJP07) did not identify any of the two genes, and reported a predicted phenotype sensitive to STR. Laboratory EJP12 reported the aminoglycoside resistance genes *aadA12*, for BACT, and *aadA8b*, for DNA; however, these genes were not identified in the reference genome by the EURL-AR pipeline, and were therefore scored as mistakes. The aminoglycoside resistance gene *aac(6')-Iaa* was identified by all participants except EJP05 and EJP08. Moreover, more than half of the participants (62% for BACT, 58% for DNA) predicted a phenotypic resistance to AMI, attributed to the presence of gene *aac(6')-Iaa*; however, this is a cryptic gene in *S. enterica*, therefore it is not expected to confer phenotypic resistance to AMI. Lastly, the amphenicol resistance gene *cmlA1* was identified by all participants apart from EJP12, which reported the gene *cml*. The specific variant of *cml*, i.e. *cmlA1*, should have been reported; therefore, reporting of *cml* was scored with zero. All laboratories predicted a phenotype resistant to CHL, apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” (see above) and EJP06. The last one identified gene *cmlA1* but did not report resistance to CHL.

Regarding the predicted AMR phenotypic profiles submitted, only one participant (EJP08) reported the expected profile (Figure 7). Six deviating AMR phenotypic profiles were reported, that mainly missed resistance to ERY and included resistance to AMI. All deviating AMR profiles submitted were evaluated as mistakes.

Table 10. Gene/gene variant data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>aph(3⁺)-Ia</i>	X	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>blaTEM-1A/B/C/D</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>cmlA1</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>dfra12</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>mcr-1.1</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>mef(B)</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>sul3</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>tet(B)</i>	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>aac(6⁺)-Iaa</i>	X	X	X	-	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>aadA1, ant(3⁺)-Ia</i>	X	-	-	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>aadA2, aadA2b</i>	X	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
<i>tet(M)</i>	X	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>aph(3⁺)-Ia</i>	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>cml</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	
<i>aadA12</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>aadA8b</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	

Figure 6. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) genes for BACT and DNA samples for *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001.

Table 11. Predicted AMR phenotype data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Ampicillin	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Azithromycin	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Chloramphenicol	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Colistin	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Erythromycin	-	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	
Kanamycin	X	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	-	X	X	-	-	
Streptomycin	X	-	-	-	X	-	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	-	-	
Sulfamethoxazole	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Tetracycline	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Trimethoprim	X	X	-	-	X	-	X	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Amikacin	X	X	-	-	X	-	-	X	X	X	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	-	-	-	-	-	X	X	X	X	X	X	

Figure 7. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) predicted AMR phenotypic profile for BACT and DNA samples, for *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001.

Figure 8. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) AMR phenotypes for BACT and DNA samples for *S. enterica* strain GENOMIC21-001.

E. coli, GENOMIC21-003

From the 15 EJP CARE laboratories, all signed up for the analysis of GENOMIC21-003-BACT and GENOMIC21-003-DNA. Overviews of the submitted data for the *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003 are presented in Table 12 and Figure 9, for AMR genes or gene variants, and in Table 13, Figure 10 and Figure 11, for the predicted AMR phenotype. Unexpected chromosomal mutations were reported for *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003 by one participant (EJP10): two mutations in gene *pmrB* (D283G, Y358N), and one in *parC* (E62K). These mutations were identified in the reference genome; however, they were not known to confer AMR and should have not been reported.

Regarding the two expected β -lactam resistance genes, *blaNDM-4* was identified by all participants, and *blaTEM-1A/B/C/D* by all but two (EJP04 and EJP13) laboratories. Predicted phenotype resistant to the β -lactams included in this PT (AMP, FEP, FOT, FOX, TAZ, ETP, IMI, MERO) was reported by the majority of participants in general, with some exceptions (see Table 13). Regarding the folate pathway antagonists, the

gene *dfrA12* as well as the predicted resistance to TMP were reported by all participants. A predicted phenotype resistant to SMX was reported by all participants, as well as the respective gene *sul3*. The gene *sul1* was also expected for this strain, and it was reported by 13 participants (EJP07 and EJP13 did not identify this gene). Lastly, the aminoglycoside resistance gene *aadA2* (or variant *aadA2b*) was identified by 80% of the participants (Figure 9), as three laboratories (EJP04, EJP07 and EJP10) did not report it. However, these three laboratories even though they did not identify any aminoglyside resistance genes, they predicted a phenotype resistant to STR, which is a paradox. Two deviating genes, *cmIA1* (EJP05) and *aadA8b* (EJP12), were reported, each by one participant; however, they were not identified in the reference genome by the EURL-AR pipeline, and were scored therefore as mistakes.

Regarding the predicted AMR phenotypic profiles submitted (Figure 10), four participants for BACT (EJP01, EJP02, EJP12 and EJP14) and five for DNA (same as BACT, plus EJP06) reported the expected profile. Four deviating AMR phenotypic profiles were reported, and the most prevalent was missing resistance to STR. All deviating AMR profiles submitted were evaluated as mistakes. Finally, resistance to GEN was reported by one laboratory (EJP03), but that was not supported by a relative genetic background, and was therefore evaluated as a mistake.

Table 12. Gene/gene variant data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>blaNDM-4</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>blaTEM-1A/B/C/D</i>	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	
<i>dfrA12</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>sul1</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	
<i>sul3</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>aadA2, aadA2b</i>	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	
<i>cmIA1</i>	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>aadA8b</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	

Figure 9. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) genes for BACT and DNA samples, *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003.

Table 13. Predicted AMR phenotypic data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Ampicillin	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Cefepime	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Cefotaxime	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Cefoxitin	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Ceftazidime	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Ertapenem	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Imipenem	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Meropenem	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Streptomycin	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Sulfamethoxazole	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Trimethoprim	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Gentamicin	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

Figure 10 Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) predicted AMR phenotypic profile for BACT and DNA samples, for *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003.

Figure 11. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) deviating (Right) AMR phenotypes for BACT and DNA samples for *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-003.

E. coli, GENOMIC21-004

From the 15 EJP CARE laboratories, all signed up for the analysis of GENOMIC21-004-BACT and GENOMIC21-004-DNA. Overviews of the submitted data for the *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-004 are presented in Table 14 and Figure 12, for AMR genes or gene variants, and in Table 15, Figure 13 and Figure 14, for the predicted AMR phenotype. Laboratory EJP14 did not analyse sample GENOMIC21-004-DNA, even though there was a sign up for this material. This is evaluated as a mistake in the webtool; however, the laboratory could exclude this sample from the internal evaluation. Four laboratories (EJP04, EJP05, EJP07 and EJP11) did not submit data on the predicted phenotype, even though AMR genes were identified (“blank-phenotype laboratories”). Moreover, unexpected chromosomal mutations were reported by one participant (EJP10): two mutations in the *pmrB* gene (D283G, Y358N) and two in *parC* (D204E, E62K). These mutations were identified in the reference genome too; however, they are not known to confer AMR and should have not been reported.

For strain GENOMIC21-004, two aminoglycoside resistance genes were expected (*aph(3'')-Ib* and *aph(6)-Id*), both related to phenotypic resistance to STR. Nine participants (60%) identified the gene *aph(3'')-Ib*, while twelve participants for BACT (80%) and eleven for DNA (73%) identified *aph(6)-Id* (Figure 12). One participant (EJP05) reported *aph(3')-Ib*, which is most likely due to a typic mistake. The same was observed for EJP13, which reported *aph(6)-Ib* and not *aph(6)-Id*. Both cases were evaluated as mistakes, due to incorrect reporting. A predicted phenotype resistant to STR was reported by all participants apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” and EJP15.

The folate pathway antagonist gene *sul2* was reported by all participants. The respective predicted resistance to SMX was reported by all participants too, apart from the ones not submitting any data, mentioned above. Finally, *tet(B)* gene was reported by all laboratories, apart from EJP012, which identified *tet(A)* instead. The *tet(A)* gene was not identified in the reference genome by the EURL-AR pipeline and was therefore evaluated as a mistake. Predicted resistance to TET was reported by all participants apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” – see above. Finally, two deviating genes were reported each by one participant: *cmIA1* (EJP05) and *str* (EJP12). The gene *cmIA1* was not identified in the reference genome, and was therefore scored as a mistake. The gene *strA* and *strB* are alternative names for genes *aph(3'')-Ib* and *aph(6)-Id* respectively; however, reporting of *str* was evaluated to be unspecific; therefore, it was scored with zero.

Regarding the predicted AMR phenotypic profiles submitted (Figure 13), seven participants for BACT (47%) and six for DNA (40%) reported the expected profile. Two deviating AMR phenotypic profiles were reported, by a small fraction of participants, and were evaluated as mistakes. Finally, resistance to KAN was reported by one laboratory (EJP08), but that was not identified by the EURL-pipeline in the reference genome.

Table 14. Gene/gene variant data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-004. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT														DNA															
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>aph(3'')-Ib</i>	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x
<i>aph(6)-Id</i>	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	x
<i>sul2</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x
<i>tet(B)</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	x
<i>aph(3')-Ib</i>	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>cmIA1</i>	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>str</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>tet(A)</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>aph(6)-Ib</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 12. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) AMR genes for BACT and DNA samples, *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-004.

Table 15. Predicted phenotype data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-004. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Streptomycin	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	x	x	-	-
Sulfamethoxazole	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x
Tetracycline	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x
Kanamycin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Figure 13 Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) predicted AMR phenotypic profile for BACT and DNA samples, for *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-004.

Figure 14. Percent of participants (n=15 for BACT and DNA) reporting expected (Left) deviating (Right) AMR phenotypes for BACT and DNA samples for *E. coli* strain GENOMIC21-004.

C. jejuni, GENOMIC21-005

From the 15 EJP CARE laboratories, 13 signed up for the analysis of GENOMIC21-005-BACT and GENOMIC21-005-DNA. Overviews of the submitted data for the *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005 are presented in Table 16, for chromosomal mutations, in Table 17 and Figure 15 for AMR genes or gene variants, and in Table 18 and Figure 16, for the predicted AMR phenotype. Four laboratories (EJP04, EJP05, EJP07 and EJP11) did not submit data on predicted AMR phenotype, even though they identified AMR mutations and genes (“blank-phenotype laboratories”). The chromosomal mutation A2075G in 23S rRNA, conferring resistance to ERY, was reported by all the participants, except for EJP03 and EJP05. Predicted resistance to ERY was reported by all the participants, apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” (see above). The *tet(O)* gene was identified by all laboratories, and resistance to TET was reported by all apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories”. The expected predicted AMR profile was reported by 62% of the participants (Figure 16).

Lastly, eight (62%) and two (15%) participants identified the genes *blaOXA-61* and *blaOXA-193* respectively, which both confer resistance to β-lactams and are indeed present in the reference genome. However, *blaOXA* genes are not known to confer resistance to ETP, which was the only β-lactam included in this proficiency test for *C. jejuni*. Therefore, these genes should not have been reported; however, since the PT 2021 protocol was not providing clear information on this issue, it was decided to blank the scores for these results.

Table 16. Chromosomal mutation data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005. Crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
A2075G	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	x	x	x

Table 17. Gene/Gene variant data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>tet(O)</i>	/	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	x	x	x
<i>blaOXA-61</i>	/	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	-	/	-	x	x	x	-	/	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	-	/	-	x	x	x	-
<i>blaOXA-193</i>	/	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	/	x	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	/	x	-	-	-	-

Figure 15. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) genes for BACT and DNA samples, *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005.

Table 18. Predicted phenotype data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Erythromycin	/	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	x	/	-	x	x	x	x	/	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	x	/	-	x	x	x	x
Tetracycline	/	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	/	-	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	/	-	x	x	x	x

Figure 16. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Middle) predicted AMR phenotypic profile, and individual AMR phenotypes (Right) for BACT and DNA samples, for *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-005.

C. jejuni, GENOMIC21-006

From the 15 EJP CARE laboratories, 13 signed up for the analysis of GENOMIC21-006-BACT and GENOMIC21-006-DNA. Overviews of the submitted data for the *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006 are presented in Table 19, for chromosomal mutations, in Table 20 and Figure 17 for AMR genes or gene variants, and in Table 21 and Figure 18, for the predicted AMR phenotype. Four laboratories (EJP04, EJP05, EJP07 and EJP11) did not submit data on predicted AMR phenotype, even though they identified AMR mutations and genes (“blank-phenotype laboratories”). The chromosomal mutation A2075G in 23S rRNA, conferring resistance to ERY, was reported by all the participants, except for EJP05. The chromosomal mutation T86I in gyrA, predicted

to confer resistance to CIP, was not identified by three laboratories (EJP04, EJP05 and EJP11). The predicted resistances to ERY and CIP were reported by all participants, apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” plus EJP03. 1. Results regarding the chromosomal mutation T86I were not evaluated because of issues regarding the reference *gyrA* gene used in the ResFinder database. Predicted phenotype resistant to CIP is not evaluated too, i.e., phenotypes resistant or susceptible to CIP were accepted.

The two expected aminoglycoside resistance genes *aph(2'')-I_f* and *aac(6')-aph(2'')*, were reported by 85 and 100% of the participants respectively (Figure 17). The following deviating aminoglycoside resistance genes were reported: *ant(6)-I_a* (62-69% of participants), *aph(3')-III* (62%) and *aph(3')-III_a* (8%). These genes are present in the reference genome; however, they do not confer resistance to any of the antimicrobials included in the present PT (Table 3). Genes *ant(6)-I_a* and *aph(3')-III* are not known to confer resistance to GEN, which is the only aminoglycoside included in the panel for *C. jejuni*. Moreover, the sequence of gene *aph(3')-III_a* is fairly closely related to gene *aph(3')-III*. The difference between the variants stems from an insertion/deletion at positions 800 and 815. Poor assembly or sequence quality in this area can cause this error. Reporting of the gene is scored with zero (score=0); however, the phenotypic resistance profile is not affected by reporting of this gene. Predicted resistance to GEN was reported by all participants apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories” – see above, corresponding to 69% (Figure 18).

The amphenicol resistance gene *cat* was reported by 85% of the participants, while the respective resistance to CHL was predicted by 46%. This is because, apart from the “blank-phenotype laboratories”, three extra laboratories did not predict this resistance phenotype (EJP09, EJP12 and EJP15). Finally, the tetracycline resistance gene *tet(O)* was reported by 62% of the participants, and resistance to TET was predicted by 38%. In the reference genome, gene *tet(O)* is present with 95% identity, which was evaluated, at a later stage, as too low; therefore, scores for *tet(O)* gene were blanked and predicted phenotypes resistant or susceptible to TET were accepted. Moreover, one participant reported gene *tet(O/32/O)*, which has relatively similar percentages of identity to *tet(O)* in the reference genome. Scores for reporting *tet(O/32/O)* were blanked for this reason.

Three more deviating genes were reported: *ant(2'')-I_a* (8% of participants in DNA), *blaOXA-61* (54%), *blaOXA-193* (23%) and *aadA9* (8%). Similarly to strain GENOMIC21-005, *blaOXA* genes are known to confer resistance to β-lactams, but not ETP, which is the only β-lactam antibiotic included in this PT for *C. jejuni*. However, since the PT 2021 protocol did not provide clear instructions on this, the scores for these results are blanked. The deviating genes *ant(2'')-I_a* and *aadA9* were not identified by the EURL-AR pipeline, either at the reference genome, or at the submitted sequence of this participant (cutoff 90% ID, 60% coverage).

Table 19. Chromosomal mutation data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

		BACT															DNA														
		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
A2075G		x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
T86I		x	x	-	-	x	x	x	x	x		-	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	x	x	x	x		-	x	x	x	x

Table 20. Gene/gene variant data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006. Grey: deviating results, crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

		BACT															DNA														
		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>aph(2'')-I_f</i>		x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>cat</i>		x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x	x		x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	x		x	-	x	x	x	
<i>tet(O)</i>		x	-	x	-	-	x	x	-		-	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	-	x	x	-		-	x	x	x	x	

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>aac(6')-aph(2'')</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>ant(2'')</i> - <i>la</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>ant(6)</i> - <i>la</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	x	-	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	x	-		
<i>aph(3')</i> - <i>III</i>	x	-	-	x	x	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	-	-	x	x	-	-	x	-	-	x	x	-	x	x	
<i>blaOXA-61</i>	x	-	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	-	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	-	
<i>aadA9</i>	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>aph(3')</i> - <i>IIIa</i>	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>blaOXA-193</i>	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>tet(O/32/O)</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	

Figure 17. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Right) genes for BACT and DNA samples, *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006.

Table 21. Predicted phenotype data submitted by each participant for the live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) of *C. jejuni* GENOMIC21-006. Crossed cells: laboratory did not participate.

	BACT															DNA														
	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Chloramphenicol	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	-	-	-	-	x	x	-		
Ciprofloxacin	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	x	x	x	x		
Erythromycin	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	-	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	x	x	x	x		
Gentamicin	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	-	x	x	x	x	x	-	-	x	-	x	x	-	-	x	x	x	x		
Tetracycline	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	-	-	-	x	x	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	x	-	x	x		

Figure 18. Percent of participants reporting expected (Left) and deviating (Middle) predicted AMR phenotypic profile, and individual AMR phenotypes (Right) for BACT and DNA samples, for *C. jejuni* strain GENOMIC21-006.

4.4. Performance evaluation for the identification of AMR determinants and predicted AMR phenotype

The performance of the participants regarding the identification of AMR chromosomal mutations was expressed as percent of the maximum obtainable score (see Table 24) and is presented in Figure 19. Laboratories achieved the maximum score for both *C. jejuni* strains, i.e., reported all mutations, apart from one (EJP05) who did not identify any mutation. The performance was identical for live culture (BACT) and pre-prepared DNA (DNA) samples. The sum of scores for AMR genes and gene variants per participant is presented in Table 22, for each strain. The collective performance of all participants for AMR gene/gene variant per strain is presented in Figure 20. For strain GENOMIC21-05 the maximum possible score was obtained, while for the other strains the values ranged from 33 to 100%. Since the number of expected genes for each strain is different, it is more likely to achieve a higher performance for strains with fewer expected AMR genes. For example, for strain GENOMIC21-005 there is only one expected gene, i.e. the maximum score per participant is 1 (Table 24). The sum of scores for predicted AMR phenotype per participant is presented in Table 23 for each strain, while the collective performance of all participants for the predicted AMR phenotype is presented in Figure 21.

Table 22. Sum of scores per participant for AMR genes, for each strain. Crossed cells: lab did not participate

		Max. Score	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
GENOMIC21-001	BACT	11	/	11	8	8	10	9	8	10	11	/	11	6	11	11	11
	DNA	11	/	11	8	8	10	/	8	10	11	/	11	6	11	11	11
GENOMIC21-003	BACT	6	6	6	6	4	6	6	4	6	6	5	6	6	4	6	6
	DNA	6	6	6	7	4	6	6	4	6	6	5	6	6	4	6	6
GENOMIC21-004	BACT	4	4	4	3	2	3	3	2	4	4	4	4	2	3	4	4
	DNA	4	4	4	3	2	3	4	2	4	4	4	4	2	3	0	4
GENOMIC21-005	BACT	1	/	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	/	1	1	1	1	1
	DNA	1	/	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	/	1	1	1	1	1
GENOMIC21-006	BACT	3	/	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	3	/	3	1	3	3	3
	DNA	3	/	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	3	/	3	1	3	3	3

Table 23. Sum of scores per participant for predicted AMR phenotype, for each strain. Crossed cells: lab did not participate

		Max. Score	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
GENOMIC21-001	BACT	10	/	9	7	0	0	9	0	10	7	/	0	8	10	9	7
	DNA	10	/	9	7	0	0	/	0	10	7	/	0	7	10	9	7
GENOMIC21-003	BACT	11	11	11	10	0	0	10	0	8	10	10	0	11	11	11	10
	DNA	11	11	11	10	0	0	11	0	8	10	10	0	11	11	11	10
GENOMIC21-004	BACT	3	3	3	3	0	0	3	0	3	3	2	0	3	3	3	2
	DNA	3	3	3	3	0	0	3	0	3	3	2	0	3	3	0	2
GENOMIC21-005	BACT	2	/	2	1	0	0	2	0	2	2	/	0	2	2	2	2
	DNA	2	/	2	1	0	0	2	0	2	2	/	0	2	2	2	2
GENOMIC21-006	BACT	3	/	3	2	0	0	3	0	3	2	/	0	2	2	3	2
	DNA	3	/	3	2	0	0	3	0	3	2	/	0	2	3	3	2

Table 24. Maximum obtainable score per participant for each category of AMR determinants (chromosomal mutations, genes, or gene variants) and the predicted AMR phenotype, as well as the total maximum score. To evaluate the performance of the participants in more detail, individual scores were assigned to each AMR phenotype submitted, instead of scoring the entire phenotypic AMR profile submitted. Scores for the elements highlighted in yellow were blanked after re-evaluation, for details see text and Table 5.

	<i>S. enterica</i>		<i>E. coli</i>				<i>C. jejuni</i>					
	GENOMIC21-001		GENOMIC21-003		GENOMIC21-004		GENOMIC21-005			GENOMIC21-006		
	Gene/Gene variant	Predicted AMR phenotype	Gene/Gene variant	Predicted AMR phenotype	Gene/Gene variant	Predicted AMR phenotype	Chr. mutations	Gene/Gene variant	Predicted AMR phenotype	Chr. mutations	Gene/Gene variant	Predicted AMR phenotype
	<i>aph(3')-Ia</i>	AMP	<i>blaNDM-4</i>	AMP	<i>aph(3'')-Ib</i>	STR	A2075G	<i>tet(O)</i>	ERY	A2075G	<i>aph(2'')-Ic</i>	CHL
	<i>blaTEM-1A/B/C/D</i>	AZI	<i>blaTEM-1A/B/C/D</i>	FEP	<i>aph(6)-Id</i>	SMX			TET	T86I	<i>cat</i>	CIP
	<i>cmIA1</i>	CHL	<i>dfrA12</i>	FOT	<i>sul2</i>	TET					<i>tet(O)</i>	ERY
	<i>dfrA12</i>	COL	<i>sul1</i>	FOX	<i>tet(B)</i>						<i>aac(6)-aph(2'')</i>	GEN
	<i>mcr-1.1</i>	ERY	<i>sul3</i>	TAZ								TET
	<i>mef(B)</i>	KAN	<i>aadA2, aadA2b</i>	ETP								
	<i>sul3</i>	STR		IMI								
	<i>tet(B)</i>	SMX		MERO								
	<i>aac(6)-Iaa</i>	TET		STR								
	<i>aadA1, ant(3'')-Ia</i>	TMP		SMX								
	<i>aadA2, aadA2b</i>			TMP								
Max score per category	11	10	6	11	4	3	1	1	2	1	3	3
Total max. score	21		17				7			7		

Figure 19. Performance of participants regarding the identification of chromosomal mutations conferring AMR in BACT and DNA samples, expressed as percent of the maximum score. Left: *C. jejuni*, strain GENOMIC21-005, Right: *C. jejuni*, strain GENOMIC21-006.

Figure 20. Performance of participants regarding the identification of AMR genes or gene variants in BACT and DNA samples, expressed as percent of the maximum score: (A) *S. enterica*, strain GENOMIC21-001, (B) *E. coli*, strain GENOMIC21-003, (C) *E. coli*, strain GENOMIC21-004, (D) *C. jejuni*, strain GENOMIC21-005 and (E) *C. jejuni*, strain GENOMIC21-006. N.p.=Not participated.

Figure 21. Performance of participants regarding the identification of predicted AMR phenotypes (individual) in BACT and DNA samples, expressed as percent of the maximum score: (A) *S. enterica*, strain GENOMIC21-001, (B) *E. coli*, strain GENOMIC21-003, (C) *E. coli*, strain GENOMIC21-004, (D) *C. jejuni*, strain GENOMIC21-005 and (E) *C. jejuni*, strain GENOMIC21-006. N.p.=Not participated.

4.5. Identification of serogroup/serotype

For the detection of serogroup/serotype for *S. enterica*, the majority of participants used SeqSero software, while for *E. coli* the majority used SerotypeFinder (Figure 23). An overview of the results is presented in Table 25. For the two *S. enterica* strains GENOMIC21-001 and GENOMIC21-002, the majority of the participants (77-85%) reported the expected serogroup O. Laboratory EJP03 submitted O7: (C1) for strain GENOMIC21-001, and O:4 (B) for GENOMIC21-002, which could be a mix up during submission. For the two *E. coli* strains, GENOMIC21-003 and GENOMIC21-004, all participants reported the expected serogroup O. For strain GENOMIC21-001, approximately 33-38% of the participants submitted the expected serotype H (I1,4,[5],12:i:-), and 46-50% of the participants submitted serotype H “Typhimurium”. This was considered as correct during re-evaluation because type I1,4,[5],12:i:- was included as an option in the webtool at a later stage, by mistake. For strain GENOMIC21-002, 62-69% of the participants submitted the expected serotype H, while one participant submitted “I1,4,[5],12:i:-”, which could potentially be a mixup with GENOMIC21-001 during submission. For the two *E. coli* strains all participants reported the expected serotype H, for both BACT and DNA samples, apart from laboratory EJP14, which did not submit data for the DNA sample for strain GENOMIC21-004.

Figure 22. Bioinformatics tool used for the detection of serogroup/serotype.

Table 25. Serogroup O and serotype H results per participant, for BACT and DNA samples. Grey: deviating results, Croseed cells: laboratory did not participate.

		BACT															DNA															
		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	
Serogroup O	GENOMIC21-001	O:4 (B)	/	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	-	x	x	/	x	x	x	/	x	x	-	x	x			
		O:7 (C1)	/	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	/	-	x	-	-	/	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-		
	GENOMIC21-002	O:7 (C1)	/	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	-	-	x	x	/	x	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	-	x	x
		O:4 (B)	/	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-	
GENOMIC21-003	O108	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		

			BACT															DNA															
			EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	
Serotype H	GENOMIC21-004	O26	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
	GENOMIC21-001	I 1,4,[5],12:i:-	/	x	-	-	x	x	-	x	-	/	-	-	-	-	x	/	x	-	-	x	/	-	x	-	/	-	-	-	-	x	
		Infantis	/	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	x	-	-	/	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-	
		Typhimurium	/	-	-	x	-	-	x	-	x	-	/	x	x	-	x	-	-	-	x	-	/	x	-	x	-	/	x	x	-	-	
	GENOMIC21-002	Infantis	/	x	-	-	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	-	-	-	x	/	x	-	-	x	x	x	x	x	x	/	x	x	-	-	x
		I 1,4,[5],12:i:-	/	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	x	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	/	-	-	-	-	-
GENOMIC21-003	H23		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
GENOMIC21-004	H11		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	-	x		

5. Concluding remarks

The EURL-AR developed the present PT in order to evaluate the *in silico* detection of AMR genes and mutations, leading to the prediction of an AMR phenotypic profile. Moreover, typing (MLST, serotype) methods were evaluated. The participating laboratories (n=15) employed individual downstream pipelines, in terms of DNA preparation, sequencing and bioinformatics tools used, to provide information regarding isolate typing and the AMR profile. Generally, the participants produced good quality of DNA sequences, independently of the pipeline used. Moreover, the participants were very successful in identifying the MLST and serotype of the isolates employed in the present PT. Regarding the *in silico* prediction of AMR, many of the participants identified the expected AMR genes and mutations; however, the data suggest that there were more uncertainties related to the predicted AMR phenotype. Evaluation of the identified AMR determinants (genes, mutations) is a crucial step to accurately predict the AMR phenotype. During data analysis in the present PT, questions related to data evaluation arose, i.e., what is the lowest accepted percent identity and coverage of a specific AMR gene that is accepted, and the presence of cryptic AMR genes, among others. Evaluation of these data contributes to the creation of a standardised genotypic approach as an alternative to the standard phenotypic susceptibility testing methods currently employed.

For future cross-sectoral PTs within this area, important considerations for the setup include which results to request, i.e., to select strains based on the actual scope of the PT. As the scientific community is still introducing WGS and learning how to apply it in the routine work also in the field of AMR, it is necessary that upcoming PT's include components that allow for participants to be guided and challenged. This is for example relevant in relation to the list of antimicrobials included in the analysis. Based on the included list of antimicrobials, it is necessary to make a thorough bioinformatics analysis, including to carefully consider the selection criteria for the genes to include as expected. As PT organizer, it is necessary to confirm for each antimicrobial that genetic mechanisms are known and can be detected by tools available to the scientific community.

Moreover, the PT-organizers should carefully consider which QC scoring to apply for the analysis of the submitted results and take into consideration the importance of script maintenance. Scripts should allow for all techniques that participants are routinely using in their laboratories, for example, the PT organizers are working with including the option to also submit reads based on long read sequencing.

The present and future work contribute to the main objective of EJP CARE project, to create a pool of reference material which can be readily used by laboratories in future PTs.

Figure 23. Expected and deviating results of Type-O and Type-H antigen identification, for the *S. enterica* strains GENOMIC21-001 (Graphs A-1 to A-4) and GENOMIC21-002 (Graphs B-1 to B-4) as well as for the *E. coli* strains GENOMIC21-003 (graphs C-1 and C-2) and GENOMIC21-004 (graphs D-1 and D-2). No deviating results were reported for Type-O or Type-H antigens for the two *E. coli* strains.

Appendix 1

DNA extraction

		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Method used (Manual DNA extraction)																
<i>S. enterica</i>	DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit, QIAGEN		x							x		x			x	
<i>E. coli</i>	DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit, QIAGEN		x							x		x			x	
	GRS Genomic DNA Kit Bacteria, GRISP (Portugal)										x					
<i>C. jejuni</i>	DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit, QIAGEN		x							x		x			x	
	QIAamp DNA Mini Kit															x

		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
Method used (Automatic DNA extraction)																
<i>S. enterica</i>	Kingfisher FLEX					x										x
	MagNA Pure 96						x									
	Maxwell 16 Instrument Promega							x								
	PSS MagLEAD 12gC (Precision System Science Co., Ltd, Chiba, Japan)								x							
	Qiagen EZ1			x												
	Qiagen EZ1 Advanced				x											
	Qiagen Qiacube connect														x	
	Qiasymphony SP													x		
<i>E. coli</i>	Kingfisher FLEX					x										x
	MagNA Pure 96						x									
	Maxwell 16 Instrument Promega							x								
	Qiagen EZ1			x												
	Qiagen EZ1 Advanced				x											
	Qiagen Qiacube connect														x	
	Qiasymphony SP												x			
	PSS MagLEAD 12gC (Precision System Science Co., Ltd, Chiba, Japan)								x							
	MaxWell RSC48	x														
<i>C. jejuni</i>	Kingfisher FLEX					x										
	MagNA Pure 96						x									
	Maxwell 16 Instrument Promega							x								
	PSS MagLEAD 12gC (Precision System Science Co., Ltd, Chiba, Japan)								x							
	Qiagen EZ1			x												
	Qiagen EZ1 Advanced				x											
	Qiagen Qiacube connect														x	
	Qiasymphony SP												x			

Library preparation

Method used		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>S. enterica</i>	Illumina DNA prep			x	x			x							x	x
	Illumina DNA Prep, (M) Tagmentation (24 samples)									x						
	Illumina Nextera DNA prep													x		
	Illumina Nextera XT		x													
	Illumina NextSeq 500/550 Mid Output Kit v2.5											x				
	Ion Xpress Plus Fragment Library Kit for AB Library Builder System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA)								x							
	Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit						x									
	Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit (96 samples)						x									
	NexteraXT													x		
(blank)	x									x						
<i>E. coli</i>	Illumina DNA prep			x	x			x							x	x
	Illumina DNA Prep, (M) Tagmentation (24 samples)									x						
	Illumina Nextera DNA prep													x		
	Illumina Nextera XT		x													
	Illumina NextSeq 500/550 Mid Output Kit v2.5											x				
	Ion Xpress Plus Fragment Library Kit for AB Library Builder System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA)								x							
	KAPA HyperPlus Kit	x														
	NEBNext® Fast DNA Fragmentation & Library Prep Set for Ion Torrent, New England Biolabs										x					
	Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit						x	x						x		
<i>C. jejuni</i>	Illumina DNA prep			x	x			x							x	x
	Illumina DNA Prep, (M) Tagmentation (24 samples)									x						
	Illumina Nextera DNA prep													x		
	Illumina Nextera XT		x													
	Illumina NextSeq 500/550 Mid Output Kit v2.5											x				
	Ion Xpress Plus Fragment Library Kit for AB Library Builder System (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA)								x							
	Nextera XT DNA Library Preparation Kit						x	x						x		
	(blank)	x										x				

Sequencing platform

		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>S. enterica</i>	HiSeq 2500												x			
	MiSeq			x	x					x				x	x	x
	NextSeq		x			x	x	x				x				
	Other								x							

		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>E. coli</i>	(blank)	x									x					
	HiSeq 2500												x			
	MiSeq			x	x					x				x	x	x
	NextSeq	x	x			x	x	x				x				
	Other								x		x					
<i>C. jejuni</i>	HiSeq 2500												x			
	MiSeq			x	x					x				x	x	x
	NextSeq		x			x	x	x				x				
	Other								x							
	(blank)	x									x					

Read length

		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15
<i>S. enterica</i>	Read length															
	150					X	X	X					X			
	151		X													
	250									X				X		X
	251			X	X										X	
	300								X							
(blank)	X									X	X					
<i>E. coli</i>	150	X				X	X	X					X			
	151		X													
	250									X				X		X
	251			X	X										X	
	300								X							
	400										X					
	(blank)											X				
<i>C. jejuni</i>	150					X		X					X			
	151		X													
	250									X				X		X
	251			X	X										X	
	300								X							
	(blank)	X					X				X	X				

Trimming of reads

		Reads trimmed?		EJP01	EJP02	EJP03	EJP04	EJP05	EJP06	EJP07	EJP08	EJP09	EJP10	EJP11	EJP12	EJP13	EJP14	EJP15	
		No	Yes																
S. enterica	No		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x			x
	Yes																x		
E. coli	No	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x
	Yes																x		
C. jejuni	No		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x			x
	Yes																x		

Appendix 2: Boxplots of the evaluated QC metrics

Metrics were selected based on previously identified metrics, which showed correlation to widely used QC metrics, N50 and number of contigs. Separated by strain and sample type. 1.5 times inter quantile range is shown in blue. 3 Standard Deviations from the mean is shown in red.

Average insert size:

Coverage of the reference chromosome:

Number of contigs > 200bp

Proportion of reads mapped to reference DNA (%)

Q-score R1

Q-score R2

Size of assembled genome compared to reference (%)

N50

NG50

Appendix 3: QC metrics

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP01	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,11	100	4830298	81,29	41,21	42,36	88115	83785	213	31,32	30,8	353	206,68	1561206	1658006	2039584	1674434	381578
EJP01	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98	100	4824931	83,38	43,01	42,43	90041	88115	205	31,4	31,06	328	212,72	1612081	1642067	1969488	1647040	327421
EJP01	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,82	99,98	5383535	83,65	42,6	43,3	100754	100754	444	31,4	31,16	884	203,14	1853285	1894002	2264318	1898628	370316
EJP01	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,81	99,98	5382942	83,98	46,31	46,91	104154	100672	434	31,52	31,15	869	206,95	2019977	2057003	2449426	2061570	392423
EJP02	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,09	99,97	5318862	90,48	35,84	35,98	137294	137294	201	32,76	32,2	304	333,86	1304266	1407846	1556040	1409404	148194
EJP02	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,68	99,98	5350386	89,46	80,66	82,31	165998	165998	315	33,05	32,67	409	216,32	3170051	3478111	3887760	3484736	409649
EJP02	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,38	99,93	4936942	89,58	28,78	28,26	96741	96171	181	32,7	32,12	254	351,22	998280	1040331	1161296	1042106	120965
EJP02	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,34	99,97	4934998	88,18	107,73	106,68	217644	217644	126	32,95	32,58	215	214,56	4005861	4205107	4768796	4211208	563689
EJP02	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,01	100	4825416	89,79	37,98	37,86	95979	95979	184	32,92	32,38	302	317,99	1310402	1349202	1502642	1375402	153440
EJP02	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,08	100	4828655	89,11	106,91	105,53	94953	94260	200	33,25	32,79	327	207,35	4054831	4132338	4637218	4141078	504880
EJP02	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,99	99,98	5392981	91,71	59,65	61,55	104433	104155	432	33,05	32,52	875	283,26	2388783	2478745	2702744	2480830	223999
EJP02	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,94	99,98	5390454	89,25	71,52	72,33	103915	103915	421	33,21	32,84	878	198,33	3172718	3225155	3613702	3227678	388547
EJP02	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,19	99,87	1982051	90,49	273,07	281,96	105783	105783	163	33,55	33,03	268	283,24	3630043	4100143	4531164	4308230	431021
EJP02	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,16	99,85	1981410	90,53	215,11	221,75	76214	76214	176	33,74	33,35	268	201,43	3109302	3483681	3848124	3605262	364443
EJP02	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,13	99,98	1743134	94,53	303,97	303,97	145202	145202	44	33,56	33	63	285,45	3786579	3786579	4005676	3793878	219097
EJP02	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,26	99,98	1745460	91,98	330,36	330,36	142033	142033	58	33,73	33,33	69	199,57	4547575	4547575	4944118	4558606	396543
EJP03	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,17	99,97	5323171	97,01	136,64	137,08	279800	224927	146	36,33	34,48	165	310,62	3171879	3418461	3523886	3420954	105425
EJP03	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,25	99,98	5327052	96,55	116,59	118,75	224389	224389	147	36,25	34,27	166	300,27	2744418	3002508	3109648	3005736	107140
EJP03	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,31	99,95	4933766	97,07	91,49	90,61	416094	416094	98	35,89	34,78	116	324,37	1997433	2094895	2158122	2097014	63227
EJP03	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,74	99,95	4954873	97,24	104,74	103,24	416094	416094	134	36,25	34,89	155	308,67	2260940	2362167	2429136	2366758	66969
EJP03	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,45	100	4846666	96,86	127,22	126,6	103087	101363	187	36,45	34,65	213	300,68	2824188	2901780	2995826	2911376	94046
EJP03	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,41	100	4844959	96,56	95,27	93,91	107612	107612	177	36,32	34,37	209	333,88	2082466	2119340	2194892	2124262	75552
EJP03	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,11	99,72	5399483	96,65	123,3	125,25	121863	121356	407	36,56	34,37	453	300,15	3167408	3233217	3345318	3236484	112101
EJP03	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,42	99,98	5416859	97,41	147,52	149,67	121863	121863	421	36,38	34,86	475	306,84	3753213	3827157	3928956	3829192	101799

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP03	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,45	99,79	1987287	95,59	96,95	104,59	109404	109404	157	36,61	35,81	170	295,43	823630	961462	1005772	988416	44310
EJP03	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,36	99,82	1985386	95,68	190,29	201	105883	105883	152	36,29	36,01	161	308,22	1585999	1815379	1897438	1865164	82059
EJP03	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,03	99,98	1741400	97,9	233,61	233,61	173466	173466	29	36,83	35,97	31	293,17	1862650	1862650	1902568	1866116	39918
EJP03	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,96	99,98	1740275	97,82	275,5	275,5	274163	274163	21	36,74	35,83	23	313,08	2142925	2142925	2190690	2146888	47765
EJP04	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,82	99,98	5358074	92,97	176,46	180,36	279800	229416	210	35,47	32,25	230	351,73	4258472	4672524	5025896	4688044	353372
EJP04	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,52	99,98	5341863	94,13	165,46	167,79	200677	200677	174	35,42	33,13	189	366,69	3908928	4256833	4522478	4266964	265645
EJP04	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	100,18	99,96	4976529	92,4	162,11	160,99	416094	416094	187	35,56	32,11	209	370,4	3631817	3825143	4139852	3841858	314709
EJP04	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,66	99,96	4950810	93,61	160,09	157,86	416094	416094	128	35,48	32,73	156	365,02	3538639	3699757	3952408	3711496	252651
EJP04	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	99,94	100	4920181	93,25	194,4	195,62	107611	107611	342	35,68	33,03	371	343,94	4372400	4546260	4875416	4598070	329156
EJP04	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,93	100	4870285	94,92	280,29	276,4	107611	107611	235	35,71	33,72	258	323,3	6290072	6404402	6747208	6424654	342806
EJP04	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,98	99,98	5448036	93,72	188,23	197,05	124691	124691	449	35,82	32,88	509	330,1	4957271	5237941	5589068	5254616	351127
EJP04	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,65	99,98	5429804	93,76	144,26	145,93	126867	121863	403	35,57	32,96	464	370,75	3770674	3833352	4088404	3843326	255052
EJP04	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	105,01	99,86	2119573	94,69	697,25	715,69	105883	109405	438	36,38	35,22	450	293,73	6007891	6849721	7233920	7023832	384199
EJP04	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,48	99,87	2008010	95,32	721,83	754,9	105883	105883	211	36,28	35,31	222	288,41	6216474	7046351	7392300	7193260	345949
EJP04	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	103,23	99,99	1797077	96,29	800,35	800,35	176417	274163	128	36,29	34,78	130	336,58	6270536	6270536	6512444	6292018	241908
EJP04	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	101,12	99,98	1760314	95,78	729,52	729,52	274163	274163	67	36,19	35,4	69	320,17	5703055	5703055	5954507,75	5717752	251452,75
EJP05	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,03	99,98	5315296	90,42	122,76	130,19	164509	164509	169	32,85	32,35	255	339,96	4391591	5010904	5542114	5016302	531210
EJP05	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,11	99,99	5319892	92,25	241,1	246,23	153422	153422	152	33,26	32,81	234	334,45	8502397	9339844	10124876	9349542	785032
EJP05	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,14	99,96	4924997	90,35	132,07	131,42	197073	183687	94	32,85	32,3	171	350,32	4430120	4670001	5168742	4677506	498741
EJP05	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,12	99,94	4923939	90,03	52,52	51,88	159806	148534	107	32,67	32,2	190	372,96	1764380	1847283	2051748	1850452	204465
EJP05	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,12	100	4830721	87,42	99,42	106,75	96190	96190	182	32,85	32,48	339	348,85	3390628	3798741	4345532	3960956	546791
EJP05	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,19	100	4833873	89,8	92,9	91,88	96190	96190	169	32,83	31,93	292	388,06	3180886	3247530	3616238	3267668	368708
EJP05	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,86	99,99	5385969	90,68	135,72	155,71	117963	117963	369	32,89	32,5	757	317,19	5386839	6288599	6934882	6295296	646283
EJP05	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,74	99,97	5379165	90,9	65,83	66,56	100804	95983	410	32,82	32,29	850	354,83	2603315	2646034	2911038	2648436	265004
EJP05	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,69	99,87	1992140	88,31	820,74	809,05	75584	75584	218	33,29	32,95	313	262,1	11307422	12754956	14442628	13400576	1687672
EJP05	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,02	99,86	1978548	90,77	573,22	574,8	105783	105783	150	33,28	32,89	237	291,29	7645032	8330077	9177404	8625602	847327
EJP05	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,46	99,98	1748907	93,29	711,34	711,34	173366	173366	67	33,29	32,89	74	301,21	8926569	8926569	9568658	8946784	642089

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP05	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,94	99,98	1739900	94,04	671,9	671,9	145078	145078	34	33,14	32,97	42	305,69	8358483	8358483	8888604	8375242	530121
EJP06	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,81	99,89	5303690	83,44	46,2	48,01	45338	44199	336	31,39	31,19	426	265,56	1807461	2019234	2420118	2021054	400884
EJP06	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,97	99,91	4916410	83,75	65,08	64,87	69919	69392	204	31,55	31,36	284	259,11	2395696	2529362	3020084	2533284	490722
EJP06	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,12	99,94	4924204	84,61	98,38	96,97	90090	88530	168	31,8	31,42	248	250,1	3607902	3769777	4455410	3775164	685633
EJP06	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,87	99,92	4818296	84,56	51,48	53,54	43004	42093	312	31,65	31,61	447	256,32	1916316	2060407	2436666	2082708	376259
EJP06	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,84	99,95	4817035	86,08	104,7	103,24	56217	56050	264	31,96	31,49	376	269,28	3848324	3918136	4551914	3924434	633778
EJP06	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,36	99,94	5358250	85,35	76,86	81,67	46896	43962	510	31,75	31,43	875	255,84	3293329	3522837	4127488	3525494	604651
EJP06	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,52	99,95	5366705	86,52	88,18	89,34	58669	54346	479	31,99	31,57	879	260,9	3758294	3828392	4424702	3830864	596310
EJP06	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,83	99,84	1974788	86,95	175,33	174,39	75584	75584	178	32,92	32,58	279	209,61	2529810	2737879	3148914	2828128	411035
EJP06	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,54	99,83	1989075	89,36	88,74	89,48	61661	61661	177	32,71	32,26	376	306,61	1210024	1323698	1481330	1375582	157632
EJP06	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,96	99,98	1740189	88,74	226,82	226,82	142033	142033	39	33,07	32,78	50	175,1	3210427	3210427	3617824	3217192	407397
EJP06	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,87	99,98	1738624	91,09	292,45	292,45	141848	141848	36	33,08	32,68	44	203,99	3932761	3932761	4317494	3941600	384733
EJP07	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,85	99,98	5305862	93,51	103,76	105,64	192280	192280	121	33,2	32,67	259	353,89	3688797	4038722	4318890	4041556	280168
EJP07	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,91	99,97	5308924	92,48	39,52	40,22	192106	192106	163	32,8	32,45	353	328,39	1418278	1552602	1678770	1553704	126168
EJP07	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,64	99,96	4950086	93,57	118,91	117,04	196803	196803	175	33,2	32,71	314	357,68	3956270	4133032	4416978	4139254	283946
EJP07	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,01	99,94	4918741	93,62	18,23	17,95	152177	149570	100	33,1	32,78	226	354,29	607852	633869	677066	634638	43197
EJP07	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,09	100	4829222	92,97	99,11	98,61	96589	96589	194	33,1	32,38	374	350,26	3383240	3475366	3738262	3481922	262896
EJP07	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,84	100	4816701	93,81	78,9	77,79	101219	96589	160	33,26	32,76	336	349,41	2669756	2717195	2896348	2722318	179153
EJP07	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,53	99,98	5367405	93,93	66,75	67,55	114049	113891	341	33,32	32,75	1042	349,06	2624390	2669210	2841592	2671196	172382
EJP07	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,44	99,98	5362452	93,73	74,97	75,61	113080	107335	314	33,16	32,74	989	342,81	2955678	2996287	3196558	2998018	200271
EJP07	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,22	99,86	1982664	93,8	304,88	319,17	132328	132328	171	33,83	33,35	334	354,78	3984885	4525296	4824366	4633492	299070
EJP07	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,53	99,85	1968563	92,49	134,16	142,25	105739	82166	130	33,8	33,28	289	338,03	1763265	2027528	2192262	2097342	164734
EJP07	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	101,44	99,98	1765966	95,7	363,44	363,44	274018	274018	137	33,79	33,31	147	350,99	4446374	4446374	4646026	4457548	199652
EJP07	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,78	99,98	1737069	96,16	303,51	303,51	274018	274018	20	33,74	33,53	27	350,53	3706143	3706143	3854038	3714628	147895
EJP08	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,76	99,96	5301065	96,16	44,75	46,93	137349	137349	143	27,73	NA	205	NA	848838	961091	999506	961419	38415
EJP08	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,71	99,97	5298520	96,51	46,21	47	223707	223707	130	27,99	NA	178	NA	878695	964224	999081	964578	34857
EJP08	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,99	99,94	4917533	96,37	51,93	51,56	201622	201622	98	27,93	NA	136	NA	913822	963723	1,00E+06	964588	36277

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP08	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,15	99,95	4925796	96,49	23,13	22,76	48128	46412	249	28,97	NA	401	NA	515542	537531	557090	538407	19559
EJP08	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,71	99,98	4810308	96,12	21,8	22,84	68497	67584	240	29,29	NA	345	NA	401660	435544	453109	439231	17565
EJP08	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,66	100	4807746	97,4	59,76	58,94	89884	89884	182	28,76	NA	232	NA	1068721	1088447	1117500	1089521	29053
EJP08	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	95,99	99,96	5337327	97,58	37,09	47,91	56738	52679	532	29,06	NA	884	NA	741196	975041	999201	975217	24160
EJP08	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,18	99,97	5348247	97,26	47,27	47,78	91931	90650	378	28,86	NA	526	NA	976372	992712	1020644	992974	27932
EJP08	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,38	99,86	1965570	92,13	45,39	48,5	104001	78859	180	27,3	NA	251	NA	367082	427971	464506	448135	36535
EJP08	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,37	99,87	1965412	92,75	55,17	57,36	132324	132324	148	27,3	NA	187	NA	450959	511055	551011	527651	39956
EJP08	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,77	99,98	1736970	95,62	43,66	43,66	130837	130837	34	26,77	NA	40	NA	337984	337984	353453	338571	15469
EJP08	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,75	99,98	1736503	96,07	76,45	76,45	141987	141987	30	27,58	NA	33	NA	580900	580900	604666	581939	23766
EJP09	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,21	99,97	5325327	93,68	98,75	105,42	271408	271408	179	34,82	32,81	197	192,44	2979187	3403683	3633138	3406762	229455
EJP09	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,34	99,97	5332198	93,95	97,64	99,41	176379	176379	191	34,77	32,43	210	237,88	2654900	2897719	3084264	2900180	186545
EJP09	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,3	99,96	4932937	92,86	114,15	114,07	444545	444545	102	34,79	31,62	122	238,36	2940807	3109293	3348458	3113892	239165
EJP09	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,33	99,96	4934606	88,81	138,42	136,52	263848	263848	105	34,44	29,67	124	209,21	3961815	4140261	4661676	4148720	521415
EJP09	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,47	100	4848103	87,15	82,62	88,37	101363	101363	210	35,06	31,73	235	247,1	2139044	2448186	2809178	2624562	360992
EJP09	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,45	100	4846976	93,74	103,89	102,46	101363	101363	210	34,32	32,1	235	241,81	2686712	2735545	2918340	2740416	182795
EJP09	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,44	99,96	5418076	94,43	58,27	74,78	116980	116980	476	34,99	32,51	535	240,74	1736697	2252728	2385508	2254642	132780
EJP09	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,45	99,97	5418436	94,21	71,7	72,47	118139	114813	451	34,94	32,38	510	252,62	2090218	2122821	2253374	2124462	130553
EJP09	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,4	99,8	1986207	96,12	92,03	95,55	109404	105883	172	35,8	35,36	183	244,76	839173	943468	981534	964076	38066
EJP09	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,44	99,82	1987095	96,33	216,25	226,76	105883	105883	174	36,38	35	185	255,64	1915976	2176806	2259756	2223956	82950
EJP09	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,92	99,98	1739593	97,84	173,18	173,18	147824	147824	24	35,74	34,5	26	248,24	1476242	1476242	1508780	1479430	32538
EJP09	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,94	99,98	1739935	97,04	213,67	213,67	142133	142133	26	36,54	33,65	28	264,51	1786092	1786092	1840496	1790236	54404
EJP10	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,48	100	4799338	98,03	136,52	134,43	93762	93762	162	28,87	NA	212	NA	2060313	2096836	2138967	2107541	42131
EJP10	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,56	100	4803293	98,43	120,89	119,08	95946	94859	165	29,01	NA	209	NA	1877204	1909714	1940213	1911127	30499
EJP10	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,38	99,98	5359285	98,36	95,38	97,03	86317	66980	405	28,98	NA	623	NA	1724900	1765576	1794989	1765806	29413
EJP10	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,19	99,99	5348279	98,16	68,48	69,09	113865	104109	364	29,29	NA	510	NA	1365252	1385307	1411241	1385563	25934
EJP11	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,17	99,98	5322925	95,93	121,14	123,47	223887	223887	161	33,93	33,76	227	326	4182260	4584734	4779238	4590622	194504
EJP11	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,08	99,97	5318047	96,02	106,14	107,32	137298	137298	150	33,91	33,75	229	349,17	3665035	3985893	4151252	3990494	165359

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP11	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,2	99,96	4928153	95,39	134,47	132,65	217634	217634	97	33,87	33,56	183	326,14	4356411	4551138	4770946	4560710	219808
EJP11	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,25	99,96	4930598	95,8	138,03	136,12	227081	227081	98	33,89	33,72	181	348,99	4464476	4668484	4873406	4678078	204922
EJP11	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,43	100	4846026	93,71	128,36	132,84	101263	99696	229	34,01	33,84	343	310,24	4218720	4524240	4827982	4660182	303742
EJP11	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,1	100	4829713	96,01	120,74	119,11	96190	96190	171	33,96	33,76	284	333,82	3980335	4053818	4222122	4062892	168304
EJP11	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,98	99,98	5392661	95,97	100,2	115,16	114093	113923	377	33,95	33,77	807	329,86	3830749	4444552	4631090	4449390	186538
EJP11	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,92	99,99	5389150	96,31	105,13	106,2	126700	121747	355	33,92	33,83	784	336,78	4014508	4075875	4231928	4079848	156053
EJP11	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,05	99,86	1979127	95,43	389,48	398,54	108815	108815	142	34,33	34,06	238	339,89	4987413	5538856	5804326	5653394	265470
EJP11	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,93	99,85	1976639	95,51	298,48	312,27	105783	105783	127	34,34	34,24	219	323,76	3815960	4331081	4534490	4435650	203409
EJP11	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,57	99,98	1750768	97,52	397,11	397,11	173367	173367	73	34,28	34,19	77	321,31	4745960	4745960	4866546	4759006	120586
EJP11	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,89	99,98	1739039	97,29	380,41	380,41	274061	274061	23	34,33	34,18	30	332,12	4557703	4557703	4684886	4570636	127183
EJP12	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,91	99,99	5308850	94,58	71,86	72,71	110622	110622	182	37,74	37,23	431	227,62	3779020	4112885	4348376	4113502	235491
EJP12	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,86	99,95	5306080	92,9	31,78	31,8	38949	37978	402	37,18	37,13	676	120,38	1794406	1931066	2078734	1931632	147668
EJP12	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	98,88	99,87	4912256	94,37	56,57	55,55	62450	61259	211	37,67	37,17	349	232,53	2763068	2874392	3045960	2876628	171568
EJP12	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,18	99,95	4927090	92,63	32,83	32,65	170751	170751	113	37,17	36,76	260	272,3	1609267	1696236	1831098	1698522	134862
EJP12	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,87	99,99	4818567	93,5	72,98	75,3	67955	67583	213	37,69	37,05	439	249,36	3612311	3849239	4116760	3878006	267521
EJP12	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,87	100	4818389	92,32	37,56	37,13	89884	88071	173	37,2	36,67	408	290,59	1855395	1893365	2050976	1900238	157611
EJP12	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	96,1	99,93	5343578	94,39	57,05	60,52	54367	48444	477	37,75	37,09	1184	235,55	3283782	3501751	3709748	3502332	207997
EJP12	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	96,37	99,98	5358614	92,4	26,84	27,66	84030	77021	406	37,17	36,63	1253	287,74	1549468	1604942	1736994	1605144	132052
EJP12	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,36	99,8	1965284	92,78	224,75	220,7	45051	45051	217	37,98	37,24	600	274,89	4348722	4640189	5001452	4736132	361263
EJP12	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	97,57	99,86	1969411	90,58	98,36	100,39	105739	105739	138	37,59	37,02	329	293,62	1891295	2094107	2311924	2171834	217817
EJP12	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,87	99,92	1738700	95,14	906,47	906,47	40947	40947	103	38,01	37,46	142	206,75	17043427	17043427	17914698	17070466	871271
EJP12	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,79	99,98	1737252	93,97	164,75	164,75	129558	129558	23	37,66	37,05	33	292,27	2946266	2946266	3135452	2953220	189186
EJP13	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,72	99,97	5352594	96,46	72,48	77,59	224389	224389	202	35,95	34,75	214	366,84	1650404	1894161	1963718	1896832	69557
EJP13	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,66	99,97	5349268	95,65	92,16	93,37	224389	224389	186	35,93	33,93	200	368,69	2130705	2316508	2421964	2319688	105456
EJP13	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,74	99,95	4954882	96	93,75	94,32	416371	416371	129	35,92	34,4	151	373,26	2011732	2145886	2235378	2149386	89492
EJP13	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,6	99,96	4947739	95,8	86,28	85,15	416094	416094	129	35,98	34,18	153	369,96	1845727	1929796	2014304	1932780	84508
EJP13	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	99,85	100	4915839	95,47	92,65	93,97	107611	107611	325	36,17	34,94	354	373,5	1993983	2089677	2188854	2118036	99177

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP13	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	99,71	100	4909005	96,35	86,26	85,06	107611	107611	321	36,19	34,78	348	369,84	1853847	1887200	1958750	1893246	71550
EJP13	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,78	99,97	5437176	96,31	74,22	79,02	121343	121343	418	36,14	34,66	475	375,78	1864282	1993285	2069592	1996168	76307
EJP13	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,78	99,97	5437007	96,23	82,08	82,91	118061	118061	450	36,3	34,52	503	356,91	2061476	2092452	2174404	2095240	81952
EJP13	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,15	99,84	2001264	97,78	240,17	242,44	109404	109404	184	37,46	36,34	196	362,16	1931246	2113454	2161358	2136180	47904
EJP13	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,44	99,83	2007220	96,85	245,53	256,72	104876	104876	207	37,58	36,9	218	328,88	2014726	2283831	2358172	2331866	74341
EJP13	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	101,59	99,98	1768597	98,75	294,76	294,76	274164	274164	84	37,45	36,83	86	354,33	2211162	2211162	2239164	2216724	28002
EJP13	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	101,14	99,98	1760727	98,53	299,11	299,11	274163	274163	68	37,55	36,57	71	359,65	2236351	2236351	2269754	2242118	33403
EJP14	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,24	99,98	5326740	93,68	113,87	111,14	271408	271408	157	34,6	29,13	175	262,32	3089390	3237735	3456310	3242942	218575
EJP14	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,33	99,98	5331544	92,14	110,94	112,59	224389	224389	182	34,79	28,94	198	237,4	3193401	3478994	3775940	3485662	296946
EJP14	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,33	99,96	4934484	92,5	124,06	121,23	444544	444544	109	34,63	28,65	125	249,65	3274399	3387860	3662712	3393406	274852
EJP14	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,64	99,96	4949822	92,06	117,59	115,99	444545	444545	127	34,69	28,44	148	254,51	3073282	3212791	3489708	3220858	276917
EJP14	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,48	100	4848178	93,03	149,76	149,34	101076	101076	209	34,95	29,54	230	247,42	3924172	4043155	4345870	4100632	302715
EJP14	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,49	100	4848660	93,18	153,46	151,38	101271	101271	204	34,8	28,86	228	263,56	3997283	4070574	4368684	4080522	298110
EJP14	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,53	99,98	5423195	93,16	139,37	146,01	121863	118062	457	34,92	28,79	523	251,05	4258116	4474915	4803254	4483000	328339
EJP14	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,08	99,81	1999919	93,63	121,03	125,09	105883	105883	189	36,46	30,49	195	232,16	1207877	1351046	1442908	1391770	91862
EJP14	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,4	99,84	1986268	93,82	131,44	139,26	107752	105883	158	36,51	30,86	167	237,08	1325878	1521883	1622148	1568394	100265
EJP14	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,04	99,98	1741617	96,43	134,08	134,08	142133	142133	34	36,45	30,91	35	236,47	1232694	1232694	1278326	1236400	45632
EJP14	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	99,95	99,98	1740049	96,94	120,48	120,48	173466	173466	24	36,4	31,19	27	252,11	1098996	1098996	1133692	1101442	34696
EJP15	GENOMIC21-001-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	101,13	99,97	5428246	95,39	79,56	89,63	176251	176251	364	35,59	33,73	379	433,74	1837824	2210871	2317632	2215630	106761
EJP15	GENOMIC21-001-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,37	99,96	5333853	92,81	35,25	36,04	231958	231958	157	34,86	29,71	175	441,49	804050	881875	950230	884288	68355
EJP15	GENOMIC21-002-BACT	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,55	99,96	4945577	94,73	91,51	92,32	416094	416094	111	35,46	33,23	134	437,55	1999385	2136673	2255518	2140754	118845
EJP15	GENOMIC21-002-DNA	<i>S. enterica</i>	99,74	99,96	4954862	91,76	37,68	37,25	444545	444545	131	34,61	29,12	154	446,16	811203	849241	925456	852760	76215
EJP15	GENOMIC21-003-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	98,5	100	4849195	93,5	68,69	68,71	107611	107611	180	35,6	32,85	201	459,59	1524366	1574186	1683572	1591432	109386
EJP15	GENOMIC21-003-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	98,62	100	4855086	93,33	41,73	41,19	102802	102802	197	34,78	30,09	216	445,57	889315	906077	970878	910334	64801
EJP15	GENOMIC21-004-BACT	<i>E. coli</i>	97,82	99,97	5439411	95,88	67,3	82,3	126867	121865	416	35,78	33,94	480	438,57	1700288	2309659	2408862	2312846	99203
EJP15	GENOMIC21-004-DNA	<i>E. coli</i>	97,52	99,96	5422424	94,1	36,81	37,45	121863	121863	415	34,87	30,44	469	439,45	897669	917827	975416	920194	57589
EJP15	GENOMIC21-005-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,95	99,79	1997272	97,63	71,27	72,58	143348	143348	150	37,15	35,7	161	488,14	564487	623107	638262	628346	15155

User	Sample_name	Organism	Size of assembled genome	Coverage of the reference chromosome	Size of assembled genome	Proportion of reads mapped to reference	Depth of coverage chromosome	Depth of coverage total DNA sequence	N50	NG50	Number of contigs >200bp	Q-score R1	Q-score R2	Total number of contigs	Average insert size	Number of reads mapped to reference chromosome	Number of reads mapped to reference DNA sequence	Number of reads	Number of reads after trimming	Number of unmapped reads
EJP15	GENOMIC21-005-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	98,76	99,81	1993526	94,2	127,94	135,13	134342	134342	152	35,9	32,83	165	431,39	962488	1100814	1168630	1130822	67816
EJP15	GENOMIC21-006-BACT	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,04	99,98	1741638	98,2	86,81	86,81	276044	276044	23	37,17	35,76	25	487,94	642169	642169	653926	643790	11757
EJP15	GENOMIC21-006-DNA	<i>C. jejuni</i>	100,44	99,98	1748570	96,1	135,09	135,09	274163	274163	36	35,67	32,81	38	448,38	951821	951821	990468	954676	38647

Appendix 4: SNP matrices

Strain GENOMIC21-001

	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP02 -BACT	0	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
EJP02 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
EJP03 -BACT	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	5
EJP03 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	7
EJP04 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6
EJP04 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	7
EJP05 -BACT	5	4	4	4	4	4	0	4	5	4	4	5	4	4	4	21	4	4	4	4	4	4	21	4	4	4	7
EJP05 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3
EJP06 -BACT	0	0	1	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
EJP07 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	8
EJP07 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	5
EJP08 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	1	3	0	1	0	5
EJP08 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	4
EJP09 -BACT	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	0	0	0	0	0	17	0	0	0	4
EJP09 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	8
EJP11 -BACT	0	0	18	1	1	1	21	1	0	3	1	3	2	18	1	0	0	0	3	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	23
EJP11 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	8
EJP12 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	4
EJP12 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	2
EJP13 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	9
EJP13 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
EJP14 -BACT	0	0	17	1	1	1	21	1	0	3	1	3	2	17	1	0	0	0	3	2	1	0	0	1	1	0	27
EJP14 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	6
EJP15 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	13
EJP15 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
reference	5	3	5	7	6	7	7	3	2	8	5	5	4	4	8	23	8	4	2	9	9	27	6	13	7	0	

Strain GENOMIC21-002

	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP02 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
EJP02 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
EJP03 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
EJP03 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP04 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP04 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP05 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
EJP05 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6

	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP06 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
EJP06 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
EJP07 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP07 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
EJP08 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
EJP08 -DNA	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
EJP09 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
EJP09 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
EJP11 -BACT	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
EJP11 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP12 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
EJP12 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP13 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP13 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP14 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP14 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP15 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
EJP15 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
reference	6	11	11	10	10	10	6	6	5	5	10	6	9	4	9	9	10	10	6	10	10	10	10	10	10	9	0

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	EJP01 -BACT	EJP01 -DNA	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP10 -BACT	EJP10 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference	
EJP01 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	2	6	
EJP01 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3	3	6	
EJP02 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	
EJP02 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	7
EJP03 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	7
EJP03 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	12
EJP04 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	7
EJP04 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	9
EJP05 -BACT	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	5	
EJP05 -DNA	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	7
EJP06 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	3
EJP06 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	6
EJP07 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5
EJP07 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	5
EJP08 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	2	0	4	4	12	
EJP08 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	2	10	
EJP09 -BACT	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	4	8	
EJP09 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	13

	EJP01 -BACT	EJP01 -DNA	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP10 -BACT	EJP10 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP10 -BACT	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	9
EJP10 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	10
EJP11 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	7
EJP11 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	9
EJP12 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	5
EJP12 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	6
EJP13 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	7
EJP13 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	12
EJP14 -BACT	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	10
EJP14 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	10
EJP15 -BACT	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	1	0	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	12
EJP15 -DNA	2	3	0	2	1	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	4	2	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	10
reference	6	6	3	7	7	12	7	9	5	7	3	6	5	5	12	10	8	13	9	10	7	9	5	6	7	12	10	10	12	10	0

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	EJP01 -BACT	EJP01 -DNA	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP10 -BACT	EJP10 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP01 -BACT	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	5	8	4
EJP01 -DNA	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	4	1	0	5	7	5
EJP02 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	3	5
EJP02 -DNA	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	5	5
EJP03 -BACT	2	1	1	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	3	10
EJP03 -DNA	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	8
EJP04 -BACT	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7
EJP04 -DNA	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	8
EJP05 -BACT	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	11
EJP05 -DNA	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	7
EJP06 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	5
EJP06 -DNA	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	2	4
EJP07 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	7
EJP07 -DNA	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	9
EJP08 -BACT	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	3	1	0	5	7	8
EJP08 -DNA	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	6	8
EJP09 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	8
EJP09 -DNA	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	10
EJP10 -BACT	1	3	1	3	1	0	1	0	1	1	2	2	1	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	0	1	3	2	0	1	1	2	4	12
EJP10 -DNA	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	3	6	10
EJP11 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
EJP11 -DNA	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	6
EJP12 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	2	6	5
EJP12 -DNA	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	4	4

	EJP01 -BACT	EJP01 -DNA	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP10 -BACT	EJP10 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP13 -BACT	3	4	1	1	2	1	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	13	
EJP13 -DNA	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	8	
EJP14 -BACT	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	2	8	
EJP15 -BACT	5	5	1	1	2	1	0	0	2	1	1	2	0	0	5	3	1	1	2	3	0	1	2	1	0	0	1	0	0	14	
EJP15 -DNA	8	7	3	5	3	2	0	1	2	2	2	2	0	0	7	6	3	2	4	6	0	0	6	4	0	1	2	0	0	18	
reference	4	5	5	5	10	8	7	8	11	7	5	4	7	9	8	8	8	10	12	10	6	6	5	4	13	8	8	14	18	0	

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	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference	
EJP02 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	13
EJP02 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	12
EJP03 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	15
EJP03 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	12
EJP04 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	15
EJP04 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	13
EJP05 -BACT	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	8
EJP05 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	9
EJP06 -BACT	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	2	1	3	1	0	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	8
EJP06 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	8
EJP07 -BACT	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	19
EJP07 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	15
EJP08 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	13
EJP08 -DNA	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	12
EJP09 -BACT	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	14
EJP09 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	13
EJP11 -BACT	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	17
EJP11 -DNA	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	15	
EJP12 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	6
EJP12 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	11
EJP13 -BACT	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	2	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	1	15
EJP13 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	14
EJP14 -BACT	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	15
EJP14 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	12
EJP15 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	13
EJP15 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	14
reference	13	12	15	12	15	13	8	9	8	8	19	15	13	12	14	13	17	15	6	11	15	14	15	12	13	14	0	

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	EJP02 -BACT	EJP02 -DNA	EJP03 -BACT	EJP03 -DNA	EJP04 -BACT	EJP04 -DNA	EJP05 -BACT	EJP05 -DNA	EJP06 -BACT	EJP06 -DNA	EJP07 -BACT	EJP07 -DNA	EJP08 -BACT	EJP08 -DNA	EJP09 -BACT	EJP09 -DNA	EJP11 -BACT	EJP11 -DNA	EJP12 -BACT	EJP12 -DNA	EJP13 -BACT	EJP13 -DNA	EJP14 -BACT	EJP14 -DNA	EJP15 -BACT	EJP15 -DNA	reference
EJP02 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
EJP02 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
EJP03 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
EJP03 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
EJP04 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
EJP04 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
EJP05 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
EJP05 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
EJP06 -BACT	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	5
EJP06 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP07 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP07 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP08 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
EJP08 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
EJP09 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
EJP09 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP11 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP11 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP12 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	
EJP12 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	
EJP13 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP13 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP14 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP14 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
EJP15 -BACT	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
EJP15 -DNA	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
reference	1	2	3	3	3	3	0	2	5	3	3	3	1	2	2	3	3	3	1	2	3	3	3	3	4	0	